

Solution of the coupled Boussinesq–Burger’s equations by reduced differential transform method

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Abstract— In this paper, the reduced differential transform method (RDTM) is utilized to obtain the approximate solution of the coupled Boussinesq–Burger’s equations. The series solution is obtained with easily computed components. A comparison is made between our results and the exact solutions. The simplicity and consistency of the proposed method are revealed. Therefore, it can be further extended to solve different types of nonlinear partial differential equations.

Keywords— reduced differential transform method, Boussinesq–Burger’s equations, partial differential equations.

I. Introduction

In the last decades, Nonlinear partial differential equations (NPDEs) have become essential tools to model complex phenomena that arising in different aspects of science and engineering such as optical fibers, fluid dynamics, plasma physics, solid state physics, hydrodynamics and acoustics. Therefore, constructing exact and approximate solutions of NLPDEs is of great importance in mathematical sciences [1-10]. Among the NPDEs, we consider the coupled Boussinesq–Burger’s equations [11-13]

$$\begin{aligned} u_t - \frac{1}{2}v_x + 2uu_x &= 0, \\ v_t - \frac{1}{2}u_{xxx} + 2(uv)_x &= 0. \end{aligned} \tag{1}$$

The functions $u(x, t)$ and $v(x, t)$ correspond to the horizontal velocity field and the height of the water surface over a bottom horizontal level. As a nonlinear long-wave equation, (1) can describe the evolution of shallow water waves and appears in the investigation of the flow of fluids in dynamical systems. Recently, many researchers have paid their attention to secure the solution of the coupled Boussinesq–Burger’s equations [11-20].

The aim of this paper is to derive the approximate analytical solution of the coupled Boussinesq–Burger’s equations via the reduced differential transform method. The layout of this article is as follows: Section 2 deals with the overview of the utilized method. In Section 3, we exploit the RDTM for solving the governing equations. Conclusions are given in Section 4.

II. Overview of the Method

As one of the most effective solution methods, the RDTM was developed by the Turkish mathematician Yildiray Keskin [21] in 2009. Since that, it has been widely used for solving various types of differential equations by many scientists [22-26].

Consider a function of two variables $u(x, t)$ and suppose that it can be represented as a product of two single-variable functions, i.e., $u(x, t) = f(x)g(t)$. In the sense of one-dimensional differential transform, one can represent the function $u(x, t)$ as follows:

$$u(x, t) = \left(\sum_{i=0}^{\infty} F(i)x^i \right) \left(\sum_{j=0}^{\infty} G(j)t^j \right) = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} U_k(x)t^k, \tag{2}$$

where, $U_k(x)$ is called t -dimensional spectrum function of $u(x, t)$.

Let us introduce the following basic definitions of the RDTM [21,22]:

Definition 2.1 If a function $u(x, t)$ is analytic and differentiated continuously with respect to time t and space x in the domain of interest, then let

$$U_k(x) = \frac{1}{k!} \left[\frac{\partial^k}{\partial t^k} u(x, t) \right]_{t=0}, \tag{3}$$

where, the t -dimensional spectrum function $U_k(x)$ is the transformed function. Note that, the lowercase $u(x, t)$ represents the original function, while the uppercase $U_k(x)$ stands for the transformed function.

Definition 2.2 The differential inverse transform of $U_k(x)$ is defined as follows:

$$u(x, t) = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} U_k(x)t^k. \tag{4}$$

Then, combining equation (3) and (4) we write

$$u(x, t) = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{k!} \left[\frac{\partial^k}{\partial t^k} u(x, t) \right]_{t=0} t^k. \quad (5)$$

From the above definitions, it can be established that the concept of the RDTM is developed from the power series expansion.

To demonstrate the key idea of the RDM, consider the following nonlinear partial differential equation, which is written in an operator form

$$Lu(x, t) + Ru(x, t) + Nu(x, t) = g(x, t), \quad (6)$$

with initial condition

$$u(x, 0) = f(x), \quad (7)$$

where, $L = \frac{\partial}{\partial t}$, R is a linear operator which has partial derivatives, $Nu(x, t)$ is a nonlinear operator and $g(x, t)$ is an inhomogeneous term.

According to the RDTM, we can construct the following recursive formula:

$$(k + 1)U_{k+1}(x, t) = G_k(x) - RU_k(x) - NU_k(x), \quad (8)$$

where $U_k(x), RU_k(x), NU_k(x)$ and $G_k(x)$ are the transformations of the functions $Lu(x, t), Ru(x, t), Nu(x, t)$ and $g(x, t)$ respectively.

From initial condition (7), we write

$$U_0(x) = f(x). \quad (9)$$

Substituting (9) into (8) and by straightforward iterative calculation, we get the following $U_k(x)$ values. Then, the inverse transformation of the set of values $\{U_k(x)\}_{k=0}^n$ gives the n-terms approximation solution as

$$\tilde{u}_n(x, t) = \sum_{k=0}^n U_k(x) t^k. \quad (10)$$

Consequently, the exact solution of (6) reads

$$u(x, t) = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \tilde{u}_n(x, t). \quad (11)$$

Some fundamental operations of the RDTM are presented in Table 1.

III. Application of the RDTM

In this section, the RDTM is implemented for solving the coupled Boussinesq–Burger’s equations given by (1) with initial conditions [13]

$$\begin{aligned} u(x, 0) &= \frac{c}{2\alpha} - \frac{\alpha}{2} \tanh(\alpha x), \\ v(x, 0) &= -\frac{\alpha^2}{2} \operatorname{sech}^2(\alpha x), \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

where α and c are constants.

Table I. The Fundamental Operations of RDTM

Functional Form	Transformed Form
$u(x, t)$	$U_k(x) = \frac{1}{k!} \left[\frac{\partial^k}{\partial t^k} u(x, t) \right]_{t=0}$
$w(x, t) = u(x, t) \pm v(x, t)$	$W_k(x) = U_k(x) \pm V_k(x)$
$w(x, t) = \alpha u(x, t)$	$W_k(x) = \alpha U_k(x)$ (α is a constant)
$w(x, t) = x^m t^n$	$W_k(x) = x^m \delta(k - n),$ $\delta(k) = \begin{cases} 1, & k = 0 \\ 0, & k \neq 0 \end{cases}$
$w(x, t) = x^m t^n u(x, t)$	$W_k(x) = x^m U_{k-n}(x)$
$w(x, t) = u(x, t)v(x, t)$	$W_k(x) = \sum_{r=0}^k V_r(x)U_{k-r}(x)$ $= \sum_{r=0}^k U_r(x)V_{k-r}(x)$
$w(x, t) = \frac{\partial^r}{\partial t^r} u(x, t)$	$W_k(x) = \frac{(k+r)!}{k!} U_{k+r}(x)$
$w(x, t) = \frac{\partial}{\partial x} u(x, t)$	$W_k(x) = \frac{\partial}{\partial x} U_k(x)$

According to the RDTM and Table 1, the differential transform of (1) reads

$$\begin{aligned} (k + 1)U_{k+1}(x) &= \frac{1}{2} \frac{\partial}{\partial x} V_k(x) - 2A_k(x), \\ (k + 1)V_{k+1}(x) &= \frac{1}{2} \frac{\partial^3}{\partial x^3} U_k(x) - 2B_k(x) - 2C_k(x), \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

where the t -dimensional spectrum functions $U_k(x)$ and $V_k(x)$ are the transformed functions. $A_k(x), B_k(x)$ and $C_k(x)$ are the transformed nonlinear terms given by:

$$A_k(x) = \sum_{r=0}^k U_r(x) \frac{\partial}{\partial x} U_{k-r}(x), \quad (14)$$

$$B_k(x) = \sum_{r=0}^k U_r(x) \frac{\partial}{\partial x} V_{k-r}(x), \quad (15)$$

$$C_k(x) = \sum_{r=0}^k V_r(x) \frac{\partial}{\partial x} U_{k-r}(x). \quad (16)$$

Starting with initial conditions (12) and by simple iterative steps, we get

$$\begin{aligned}
 U_0(x) &= \frac{c}{2\alpha} - \frac{\alpha}{2} \tanh(\alpha x), \\
 U_1(x) &= \frac{c\alpha}{2 \cosh(\alpha x)^2},
 \end{aligned} \tag{17}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 U_2(x) &= \frac{c^2 \alpha \sinh(\alpha x)}{2 \cosh(\alpha x)^3}, \\
 &\vdots
 \end{aligned}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned}
 V_0(x) &= -\frac{\alpha^2}{2} \operatorname{sech}^2(\alpha x), \\
 V_1(x) &= -\frac{\alpha^2 c \sinh(\alpha x)}{\cosh(\alpha x)^3},
 \end{aligned} \tag{18}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 V_2(x) &= -\frac{1}{2} \frac{\alpha^2 (2 \cosh(\alpha x)^2 - 3) \alpha^2}{\cosh(\alpha x)^4}, \\
 &\vdots
 \end{aligned}$$

and so on. Similarly, we can acquire the rest of components with the aid of MAPLE software.

Taking the inverse transformation of the sets $\{U_k(x)\}_{k=0}^n$ and $\{V_k(x)\}_{k=0}^n$ yields the following n-terms approximate solutions:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \tilde{u}_n(x, t) &= \sum_{k=0}^n U_k(x) t^k \\
 &= \frac{c}{2\alpha} - \frac{\alpha}{2} \tanh(\alpha x) + \frac{c\alpha}{2 \cosh(\alpha x)^2} t \\
 &+ \dots + \frac{1}{n!} \left[\frac{\partial^n}{\partial t^n} \left(\frac{c}{2\alpha} - \frac{\alpha}{2} \tanh(\alpha x - ct) \right) \right]_{t=0} t^n,
 \end{aligned} \tag{19}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \tilde{v}_n(x, t) &= \sum_{k=0}^n V_k(x) t^k \\
 &= -\frac{\alpha^2}{2} \operatorname{sech}^2(\alpha x) - \frac{\alpha^2 c \sinh(\alpha x)}{\cosh(\alpha x)^3} t + \dots \\
 &+ \frac{1}{n!} \left[\frac{\partial^n}{\partial t^n} \left(-\frac{\alpha^2}{2} \operatorname{sech}^2(\alpha x - ct) \right) \right]_{t=0} t^n.
 \end{aligned} \tag{20}$$

Accordingly, the exact solutions of (1) read

$$\begin{aligned}
 u(x, t) &= \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \tilde{u}_n(x, t) = \frac{c}{2\alpha} - \frac{\alpha}{2} \tanh(\alpha x - ct), \\
 v(x, t) &= \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \tilde{v}_n(x, t) = -\frac{\alpha^2}{2} \operatorname{sech}^2(\alpha x - ct).
 \end{aligned} \tag{21}$$

In order to measure the validity of the resultant solutions, we plot the 4th order approximate solutions in Fig. 1 and Fig. 2. Also, the absolute errors are listed in Table 2 and depicted

in Fig. 3 and Fig. 4. One can see that the approximate solutions are accurate in comparison with the exact solutions.

IV. Conclusions

In this work, the reduced differential transform method is well availed to acquire the approximate analytical solution of a nonlinear long-wave equation, namely the coupled Boussinesq–Burger’s equations. The numerical results are presented accompanied by 3D graphics. A comparison is made between the approximate solution and the exact solution to demonstrate the validity of the first one. It is observed that the computational work of this approach is smaller than other existing ones. Various NLEEs might be investigated by the RDTM in future works.

Fig. 1. 3D profile of $\tilde{u}_4(x, t)$ when $c = 1$ and $\alpha = -1$.

Fig. 2. 3D profile of $\tilde{v}_4(x, t)$ when $c = 1$ and $\alpha = -1$.

Fig. 3. 3D profile of the absolute error of $\tilde{u}_4(x, t)$ when $c = 1$ and $\alpha = -1$.

Fig. 4. 3D profile of the absolute error of $\tilde{v}_4(x, t)$ when $c = 1$ and $\alpha = -1$.

Table II. The Absolute Errors of $\tilde{u}_4(x, t)$ and $\tilde{v}_4(x, t)$ for Various Values of t and x When $c = 1$ and $\alpha = -1$

t	x	$ u(x, t) - \tilde{u}_4(x, t) $	$ v(x, t) - \tilde{v}_4(x, t) $
0.1	-2	2.42000×10^{-8}	2.30000×10^{-9}
	-1	2.40600×10^{-7}	5.56100×10^{-7}
	0	6.63910×10^{-7}	1.88000×10^{-7}
	1	2.22400×10^{-7}	5.73700×10^{-7}
	2	2.36000×10^{-8}	6.91000×10^{-9}
0.3	-2	5.78000×10^{-6}	9.37800×10^{-7}
	-1	6.26378×10^{-5}	1.24797×10^{-4}
	0	1.56306×10^{-4}	1.31519×10^{-4}
	1	4.92939×10^{-5}	1.39100×10^{-4}
	2	5.69220×10^{-6}	2.49745×10^{-6}
0.5	-2	7.23781×10^{-5}	3.74940×10^{-5}
	-1	8.45610×10^{-4}	1.37640×10^{-3}
	0	1.89191×10^{-3}	2.60947×10^{-3}
	1	5.76568×10^{-4}	1.74699×10^{-3}
	2	7.16051×10^{-5}	3.97898×10^{-5}

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